

HIGH VELOCITY IMPACT ON CFRP

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SUMMARY

Thermodynamically consistent damage model for fibre reinforced composites was proposed and coupled with the rest of constitutive model. Constitutive model was capable of describing shock propagation in orthotropic materials. Proposed damage model and constitutive model were implemented into Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory DYNA3D nonlinear hydrocode. The observed results were validated against three dimensional impact experimental data.

Keywords: shock wave, damage, composites, stress decomposition, hydrocode

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are of significant importance in many applications, including the aerospace industry, due to their strength to weight ratio. However the design of aircraft composite structures is limited by the lack of understanding of composite materials, especially their response to high rate dynamic loading, such as high velocity impacts. The complexity arises from factors including the extreme level of anisotropy, heterogeneity, stress transfer factors etc. Due to these uncertainties, modern simulation tools are limited in their capability to predict the material degradation, its progression and failure for composites.

Three challenging areas in the modelling of the dynamic behaviour of composite structures and materials can be identified:

- modelling damage and failure including damage induced by shock wave propagation from the zone of impact
- modelling the formation and propagation of shock waves in an anisotropic material
- the modelling of damaged and failed material areas for the purpose of residual strength assessment and for structural health monitoring

This paper investigates modelling of shock wave propagation and damage in composite material undergoing extreme dynamic loading. More specifically, the material of the interest is Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) laminates of the type commonly used in aerospace engineering. The paper describes the physical background of the equation of state, a model for damage evolution and failure in composites under high-

rate loading, implementation of proposed model and coupling with the rest of the constitutive model. Results obtained with the proposed model are compared with the available experimental results.

CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

Shock wave propagation through material

A constitutive model, capable of modelling shock wave propagation through a material comprises two parts: an equation of state (EOS) which determines the material response under compression and a shear part, responsible for shear deformation. This decomposition is relatively simple for isotropic material, since the spherical part of stress tensor and strain tensor are co-linear and orthogonal to the deviatoric plane. However, in the case of anisotropic material orthogonality does not hold because the spherical component of stress can produce change in shape – deviatoric strain. The first attempt to solve the problem was by Anderson [1], but the proposal failed to predict material response accurately [2]. Thus an alternative decomposition of stress was proposed, and the principle equations governing the decomposition are summarised below.

The complexity of an orthotropic material lays in the fact that 9 parameters of stiffness and compliance matrix have to be defined. Constitutive relations for an orthotropic material can be mathematically represented using either stiffness or compliance form:

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl} \varepsilon_{kl} \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = C_{ijkl}^{-1} \sigma_{kl} = B_{ijkl} \sigma_{kl} \quad (2)$$

where σ_{ij} and ε_{kl} are stress and strain tensor and C_{ijkl} and B_{ijkl} are stiffness and compliance matrices, respectively. The new decomposition introduces a pressure as a state of stress induced by the volumetric part of strain only. Physically, this defines pressure as a vector in the stress space which is not collinear with hydrostat. Thus, one can write the equation:

$$-\hat{P}\psi_{ij} = C_{ijkl} \delta_{kl} \varepsilon_{ss} / 3 = C_{ijkk} \varepsilon_v \quad (3)$$

where direction of the pressure in the stress space is defined by tensor ψ_{ij} and volumetric strain is given as $\varepsilon_v = \varepsilon_{ss} / 3$. Tensor ψ_{ij} has diagonal members only, so indices in the brackets imply no summation.

The governing equations of the decomposition of the stress tensor are summarised below. The first equation in (4) decomposes the stress onto the components $\hat{P}\psi_{ij}$ and \hat{S}_{ij} which are not mutually orthogonal. Therefore the second equation in (4) is used where the orthogonality holds. The components which exist in (4) are given in

$$\sigma_{ij} = -\hat{P}\psi_{ij} + \hat{S}_{ij} = -\tilde{P}\psi_{ij} + \tilde{S}_{ij} \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_{ij}\psi_{ij} = -\hat{P}\psi_{ij}\psi_{ij} + \hat{S}_{ij}\psi_{ij} = -\tilde{P}\psi_{ij}\psi_{ij} + \tilde{S}_{ij}\psi_{ij} \quad (5)$$

$$\tilde{P} = \hat{P} - \frac{\hat{S}_{ij}\psi_{ij}}{\psi_{kl}\psi_{kl}} = \hat{P} - \hat{S} = -\frac{\sigma_{ij}\psi_{ij}}{3} \quad (6)$$

$$\tilde{S}_{ij} = \hat{S}_{ij} - \frac{\hat{S}_{kl}\psi_{kl}}{\psi_{sr}\psi_{sr}}\psi_{ij} = \hat{S}_{ij} - \hat{S}\psi_{ij}, \quad (7)$$

$$\tilde{S}_{ij} = \sigma_{ij} - \frac{\sigma_{kl}\psi_{kl}}{\psi_{sr}\psi_{sr}}\psi_{ij} = \sigma_{ij} + \tilde{P}\psi_{ij} \quad (8)$$

This decomposition was implemented into Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) code DYNA3D [3] and coupled with an orthotropic elastic constitutive model.

Damage model

Damage is assumed to be an irreversible process; to define it within the framework of thermodynamics, one has to start from the second law of thermodynamics which is expressed as Clausius-Duhem inequality of the form:

$$\dot{s} \geq \frac{r}{T} - \frac{1}{\rho} \operatorname{div} \frac{\mathbf{q}}{T} \quad (9)$$

where:

- s is entropy,
- r is strength of internal heat source,
- T is temperature,
- ρ is density,
- \mathbf{q} is heat flux.

Using well known relation between the internal energy and Helmholtz free energy, (10), the inequality given above (9) can be written as:

$$\psi = u - Ts \quad (10)$$

$$\dot{u} - \dot{\psi} - \dot{T}s - r + \frac{1}{\rho} \operatorname{div} \frac{\mathbf{q}}{T} - \frac{\mathbf{q}}{\rho T} \cdot \operatorname{grad} T \geq 0 \quad (11)$$

Making use of the first law of thermodynamics:

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \sigma_{ij} \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij} - \dot{\psi} - \dot{T}s - \frac{\mathbf{q}}{\rho T} \cdot \operatorname{grad} T \geq 0 \quad (12)$$

The Helmholtz - free energy is a function of the elastic and inelastic strain, temperature and structural damage, where damage is introduced with parameter ω . The time derivative is defined as:

$$\dot{\psi} = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \varepsilon_{ij}^e} \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^e + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \varepsilon_{ij}^{in}} \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^{in} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial T} \dot{T} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \omega} \dot{\omega} \quad (13)$$

In the equation above, an additive decomposition of the strain tensor is assumed:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij}^e + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij}^{in} \quad (14)$$

Substituting the last two equations into the inequality (12), the irreversible process is defined as:

$$\gamma = \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{ij} - \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij}^{in}} \right) \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{ij}^{in} - \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \omega} \dot{\omega} - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\mathbf{q} \cdot \text{grad} T}{T} \geq 0 \quad (15)$$

The terms in the inequality above represent three different mechanisms of energy dissipation: rate of mechanical dissipation; rate of damage induced dissipation, and thermal dissipation, respectively. It is assumed that dissipative rates are decoupled and positive.

This investigation is focused on dissipation due to damage and its influence on material response for dynamic loading. Damage induced dissipation is a function of the rate of change of the damage parameter, $\dot{\omega}$, and functional dependence of free energy in regard to damage parameter, i.e.:

$$\gamma_{dam} = - \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \omega} \dot{\omega} \geq 0 \quad (16)$$

Damage parameters are obtained using modified Tuler Bucher criterion [4]. Originally, Tuler Bucher proposed a criterion for failure:

$$\phi = \int_0^{t_{cr}} f(\sigma(t)) dt \quad (17)$$

where f can be any convenient function of stress. usually $(\sigma - \sigma_0)^\lambda$, σ_0 is a threshold stress below which no failure occurs, and t_{cr} is time to failure. The method was proposed for unidirectional loading, so in order to apply the method to three dimensional loading conditions an effective value for the stress was used. Delamination was modelled by an in-plane criterion based on the out of plane (through thickness) normal stress component. The function $f(\sigma(t))$ is normalized with the corresponding member of the material stiffness matrix. Evolution of the damage parameters is defined as:

$$\dot{\omega} = \dot{\omega}(\omega, \sigma) = \Omega_\omega \left(\frac{\sigma}{C_m(1-\omega)} - \frac{\sigma_{CR}}{C_m} \right) H \left(\frac{\sigma}{C_m(1-\omega)} - \frac{\sigma_{CR}}{C_m} \right) \quad (18)$$

$$\dot{\omega}_{del} = \dot{\omega}_{del}(\omega, \sigma) = \Omega_{del} \left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{C_{33}(1-\omega_3)} - \frac{\sigma_{CRdel}}{C_{33}} \right) H \left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{C_{33}(1-\omega_3)} - \frac{\sigma_{CRdel}}{C_{33}} \right) \quad (19)$$

where:

- Ω_ω , Ω_{del} are material parameters – rate of damage evolution,
- σ and σ_{33} are in-plane effective stress and out of plane stress respectively,

- σ_{CR} and σ_{CRdel} are critical in plane stress and critical out of plane stress,
- C_m and C_{33} are maximum in-plane stiffness member and through the thickness coefficient respectively,
- H is Heaviside function.

Integration of the equations (18) and (19) gives the damage parameters, which are then used to degrade the stiffness matrix. Hence, the damage parameters for three orthogonal directions are updated using the following equations:

$$\omega_1 = \omega_1 + \dot{\omega}_1 dt \quad (20)$$

$$\omega_2 = \omega_2 + \dot{\omega}_2 dt \quad (21)$$

$$\omega_{del} = \omega_{del} + \dot{\omega}_{del} dt \quad (22)$$

where ω_1 and ω_2 correspond to the fibre direction, and ω_{del} is damage parameter in the out of plane direction. Stiffness matrix of damaged material is calculated using the energy equivalence principle [5], i.e.:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{C}} = \mathbf{M}(\omega)^{-1} : \mathbf{C} : \mathbf{M}(\omega)^{-T} \quad (23)$$

where $\mathbf{M}(\omega)$ is the damage effect tensor and \mathbf{C} is the stiffness matrix of virgin material. These tensors are defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{M}(\omega)^{-1} = \text{diag} \left[\begin{array}{ccc} 1-\omega_1 & 1-\omega_2 & 1-\omega_3 \\ \sqrt{(1-\omega_1)(1-\omega_3)} & \sqrt{(1-\omega_3)(1-\omega_1)} & \sqrt{(1-\omega_1)(1-\omega_2)} \end{array} \right]$$

$$\tilde{C}_{11} = C_{11}(1-\omega_1)$$

$$\tilde{C}_{22} = C_{22}(1-\omega_2)$$

$$\tilde{C}_{33} = C_{33}(1-\omega_3)$$

$$\tilde{C}_{12} = C_{12}\sqrt{(1-\omega_1)(1-\omega_2)}$$

$$\tilde{C}_{23} = C_{23}\sqrt{(1-\omega_2)(1-\omega_3)}$$

$$\tilde{C}_{31} = C_{31}\sqrt{(1-\omega_3)(1-\omega_1)}$$

Once the damaged stiffness matrix is calculated, the stress is updated again, to account for damage effects. The proposed damage model has been implemented into the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) code DYNA3D [3] and coupled with an orthotropic elastic constitutive model explained in the previous section.

EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

Results from two experiments were used for model validation: a plate impact test [6] and a steel sphere penetration of a CFRP laminate [7]. In the both experiments, the material of the target plates was a woven CFRP laminate which is widely used in

aerospace engineering. The composite laminate was modelled as a quasi-orthotropic material with equivalent material properties given in [2].

The plate impact test was modelled as a uniaxial strain state, with the assumption that process was adiabatic. Impact at 504m/s generated shock wave propagation through thickness of the composite plate. The thickness of the plate was 3.8mm with the layup $[0/90, \pm 45]_4$. A schematic representation of finite element model is given in Figure 1.

Comparison of the experimental and numerical results obtained with and without the damage model is shown in Figure 2. The magnitude of stress in the impact direction (Z direction) and the pulse length for the both numerical models agreed well with the experimental findings. However the two numerical signals are different at the end of the pulse. The stress obtained without damage overestimates the experimental curve, which can be explained by absence of damage. When damage was incorporated, the damage initiation was captured well, but the rate of change of stress (slope of the curve) still differs from the experimental data.

Figure 1 Finite element model of plate impact test on composite target.

Figure 2 Stress trace from the back of composite plate and numerical results in the impact direction

The second model is the impact of a steel sphere on a woven CFRP laminate. The sphere was fully annealed stainless steel with a diameter of 12 mm. The steel is assumed to be isotropic. Impact at 1199m/s was normal to the target and the fibre plane. High velocity impact response is dominated by local effects, so the dimensions of the model of the target plate were chosen not to represent the dimensions of the real specimen, but just to avoid the boundary effects. The target plate is 6mm thick, consisting of 16 plies with an asymmetric lay up [7]. Finite element model of the quarter of the problem is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 FE model of sphere penetration impact

Figure 4 Damage distribution in the CFRP laminate at end of simulation.

The calculated damage distribution in the CFRP composite target is shown in Figure 4 and compared to the experimental results observed through C scans, Figure 5. The numerical results compare well with the experimental observation:

- calculated average diameter of the hole differs below 8%,
- the hourglass shape of delaminated zone is captured within the simulation,
- a bigger delamination zone at the back of the target plate compared to the front and the middle plies,

- the radius of the numerical delamination zone at the back of the target differed by less than 5% from the experimental result

Figure 5 Comparison of numerical and experimental results [7] for damage distribution within the CFRP target impacted at 1199m/s

CONCLUSION

Modelling of damage in composite materials is a challenging task and modern simulation tools are limited in their capability to predict it. This paper proposes a modified Tuler-Bucher criterion to model the process of damage and failure in composite materials undergoing extreme dynamic loading. The proposed damage model was incorporated within a constitutive model, and implemented in an explicit finite element code. The results of two numerical analyses are shown: plate impact test and sphere impact penetration. The prediction of the model with damage agreed well with experimental observations, especially in the simulation of the sphere penetration. There was a slight discrepancy between the results for plate impact which will be studied further.

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